

Satisfaction and Emotional Responses as Factors in Behavioral Intentions of New Guests of DOT-Accredited Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas

Michael H. Rioga¹ & John Vincent I. Manalo²

¹University of Iloilo, Iloilo, Philippines; ²Iloilo State College of Fisheries, Barotac Nuevo, Iloilo, Philippines

ABSTRACT

This study analyzed the level of satisfaction of first-time visit customers of DOT-accredited ecotourism destinations in Western Visayas. The Philippines in terms of the service environment, product and service quality, and their response to those mentioned earlier or their behavioral intention (intention to return, switch, or recommend) towards the overall experience. There were specific issues that the researchers focused on; these were the managerial implications that the researchers wanted to develop and the ways how to be of help to existing and upcoming ecotourism sites in handling niche ecotourism destinations, especially about their managerial skills and capabilities. The researchers gathered the data through survey questionnaires, applying purposive and quota sampling to select targeted respondents. The result showed that new guests were satisfied and positively responded to ecotourism destinations. They would most likely recommend the selected Department of Tourism accredited ecotourism destinations in Western Visayas and prove that they have exceeded their expectations.

Keywords: *Satisfaction Level, Emotional Response, Behavioral Response, Western Visayas*

INTRODUCTION

Despite its progressive cities, Western Visayas is also endowed with a rich wellspring of ecology, culture, and natural heritage sites such as beautiful caves, marine life, rock formations, offshore islets, coves, waterfalls, and crystal-clear waters surrounding the island. Tourists visiting Western Visayas enjoy many activities aside from festivals, foods, and visits to religious and heritage spots depicting the culture and history of the province; many can also indulge in swimming, snorkeling, cave exploration, hiking, mountaineering, island hopping and have a beautiful panoramic view of the islets.

However, considering that ecotourism is one of the fastest-growing sectors of the largest industry on earth (Taylor et al., 2003), it is also faced with commercialization. For the ecotourism destination to survive, it needs sources of funds to support its projects, programs, and developments; thus, technically, it will open its doors to tourists by providing them with convenient elements such as food, accommodation, amenities, facilities, and services.

Because of its many restrictions to attain sustainability, few amenities and facilities, accessibility concerns, level of service quality, technological challenges, and concerns of carrying capacity, the researcher would like to know how likely a first-time visitor would revisit and recommend the eco-destination or instead switch to another choice of destination.

The researcher also wanted to verify if the consistency of ecotourism destinations' atmosphere, environmental attributes, and services affect guests' behavioral intentions: the intention to return, recommend, or switch (Jaafar, 2010). Also, the researcher wanted to see if the quality of the ecotourism destination provides for its first-time guests and its related attributes, e.g., the service environment, aesthetic appeal, and service quality, were also considered factors in adding up to the guest's overall ecotourism experience that could lead to a decision whether to return or not.

The focus of the study is to examine whether the aesthetics and the quality of services of DOT-accredited ecotourism destinations in Western Visayas have a relative impact on the customer's intention to return.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This descriptive-correlational study aimed to determine first-time guests' satisfaction levels, emotional response, and behavioral intention in significant ecotourism destinations in Western Visayas. The descriptive-correlational method of research was employed in this investigation. Fraenkel and Wallen (2011) explained that the significant purpose of survey research is to describe the characteristics of a population. In essence, information is collected from a group of people to describe some aspects or characteristics (such as abilities, opinions, attitudes, and/or knowledge) of the population the group is part of. In correlation research, sometimes called associative research, the relationships among two or more variables are studied without any attempt to influence them. In their simplest form, correlational studies investigate the possible relationships between the two variables, although investigations of more than two variables are joint.

Participants/Respondents. The respondents of this study were the randomly selected ten (10) first-time guests or visitors for every DOT-accredited ecotourism destination in Western Visayas.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents According to Ecotourism Sites

Ecotourism Sites	Frequency (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)
Ephrathah Farms	10	20
Orchard Valley	10	20
Owataks Herb Farm and Resort	10	20
Rapha Valley Place of Wellness	10	20
Penalosa Farms	10	20
Total	50	100

Data Collection Procedure. The researcher has obtained permission from the coordinators of the ecotourism sites selected for this study. The researcher has validated and tested the researcher-made questionnaire for reliability to secure the psychometric soundness of the tool. Upon approval, the questionnaires were administered to the respondents. The researcher tabulated the raw data, which was sent to the statistician for analysis.

Data Analysis Procedure. The data collected for this study were analyzed statistically to provide answers to the problem adhered. Statistical software was used to process the data that was gathered.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Satisfaction Level of First-time Guests in DOT-Accredited Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas

Data in Table 2 revealed that, generally, the First-time guests in DOT-accredited ecotourism destinations in Western Visayas were *satisfied* as assessed by the respondents with a mean of 4.19.

In terms of gender, both males and females were satisfied; 25 years old and below were moderately satisfied, 26 years to 35 years old, 36 years to 45 years old, 46 years to 55 years old, and 56 years and above were all satisfied. It is observed that the 25 and below age group has less interest in ecotourism destinations considering that they prefer going to tourism destinations that provide more fun and adventure. Moreover, in terms of educational attainment, Bachelor's Degrees, Master's Degrees, Doctorate degrees, and others were satisfied. Lastly, as with the monthly salary of respondents from below P14,999 to P45,000 and above were all satisfied.

Table 2. Satisfaction Level of New Guests in DOT Accredited Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas

Categories	Mean	Interpretation
Entire Group	4.19	Satisfied
Gender		
Male	4.02	Satisfied
Female	3.9	Satisfied
Age		
25 yrs old and below	2.63	Moderately Satisfied
26 – 35 yrs old.	3.9	Satisfied
36 – 45 yrs old.	4.1	Satisfied
46 – 55 yrs old.	4.1	Satisfied
56 yrs and above	3.73	Satisfied
Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree	3.82	Satisfied
Master's Degree	4.13	Satisfied
Doctorate's Degree	3.90	Satisfied
Others	3.56	Satisfied
Monthly Salary		
Php 14,999.00 and below	3.91	Satisfied
Php 15,000.00 - 24,999.00	3.78	Satisfied
Php 25,000.00 – 34,999.00	3.91	Satisfied
Php 35,000.00 – 44,999.00	4.21	Satisfied
Php 45,000.00 and above	3.63	Satisfied

Emotional Response of First-time Guests in DOT-Accredited Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas

Data in Table 4 revealed that the First-time guests exhibited *moderate positive emotion* as assessed by the respondents taken as an entire group with a mean of 3.69.

Regarding gender, females and males exhibited moderate positive emotion; below 25 years old exhibited a neutral emotion, 26 years to 35 years old, 36 years to 45 years old and 46 years to 55 years old, and above 56 years old exhibited moderate positive emotion. Again, the 25 and below age group exhibited neutral emotion, which means neither positive nor negative emotion. Perhaps, there must be some aspects of ecotourism destinations that could have attracted the said group, which balances their less likely interest in the ecotourism sites. Moreover, regarding educational attainment, Bachelor's Degree, Master's Degree, Doctorate Degree, and others exhibited moderate positive emotion. Lastly, the monthly salary of respondents below P14,999 and P15,000 to 24,999, P 25,000 to 34,999, P35,000.00 to 44,999, and above P45,000 have all exhibited moderate positive emotion.

Table 4. Emotional Response of First-time Guests in DOT-Accredited Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas

Categories	Mean	Interpretation
Entire Group	3.69	Moderate Positive Emotion
Gender		
Male	3.19	Moderate Positive Emotion
Female	3.26	Moderate Positive Emotion
Age		
25 yrs old and below	2.61	Neutral
26 – 35 yrs old.	3.62	Moderate Positive Emotion
36 – 45 yrs old.	3.55	Moderate Positive Emotion
46 – 55 yrs old.	3.73	Moderate Positive Emotion
56 yrs and above	3.49	Moderate Positive Emotion
Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree	2.87	Moderate Positive Emotion
Master's Degree	3.89	Moderate Positive Emotion
Doctorate's Degree	3.36	Moderate Positive Emotion
Others	3.29	Moderate Positive Emotion
Monthly Salary		
Php 14,999.00 and below	3.18	Moderate Positive Emotion
Php 15,000.00 - 24,999.00	2.76	Moderate Positive Emotion
Php 25,000.00 – 34,999.00	3.53	Moderate Positive Emotion
Php 35,000.00 – 44,999.00	3.47	Moderate Positive Emotion
Php 45,000.00 and above	3.57	Moderate Positive Emotion

Behavioral Intentions of First-time Guests in DOT-Accredited Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas

Data in Table 5 revealed that the First Time Guests in DOT-accredited ecotourism destinations in Western Visayas moderately *agreed* as assessed by respondents who were taken as an entire group with a mean of 4.28.

In terms of gender, females, and male strongly agree; below 25 years old and 26 years to 35 years old agree; 36 years to 45 years old, 46 years to 55 years old, and above 56 years old moderately agree. Moreover, in terms of educational attainment, Bachelor's Degrees and Master's Degrees, Doctorate Degrees, and others moderately agree. Lastly, as with the monthly salary of respondents below, P14,999 were agreed, P15,000 to 24,999, P 25,000 to 34,999, P35,000.00 to 44,999, and above P45,000 were moderate.

Table 5. Behavioral Intentions of First-time Guests in DOT-Accredited Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas

Categories	Mean	Interpretation
Entire Group	3.91	Moderately Agree
Gender		
Male	4.12	Moderately Agree
Female	4.03	Moderately Agree
Age		
25 yrs old and below	3.1	Agree
26 – 35 yrs old.	3.33	Agree
36 – 45 yrs old.	4.02	Moderately Agree
46 – 55 yrs old.	4.11	Moderately Agree
56 yrs and above	4.19	Moderately Agree
Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree	3.63	Moderately Agree
Master's Degree	4.04	Moderately Agree
Doctorate's Degree	4.11	Moderately Agree
Others	4.17	Moderately Agree
Monthly Salary		
Php 14,999.00 and below	3.12	Agree
Php 15,000.00 - 24,999.00	4.2	Moderately Agree
Php 25,000.00 – 34,999.00	4.03	Moderately Agree
Php 35,000.00 – 44,999.00	3.96	Moderately Agree
Php 45,000.00 and above	3.78	Moderately Agree

Differences in the Satisfaction Level of First-time Guests in Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas according to gender.

The *t*-test results in Table 6 showed significant differences in the satisfaction level of first-time guests in ecotourism destinations in Western Visayas grouped according to gender. This is shown in the *p*-value results of 0.012.

Table 6. *t*-test Results for the Differences in the Satisfaction Level of First-time Guests in Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas Grouped According to Gender

	Mean	<i>t</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation
Gender				
Male	4.02	41.76*	0.012	Significant
Female	3.9			

Differences in the Satisfaction Level of First-time Guests in Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas according to age.

The one-way ANOVA results in Table 7 revealed that the satisfaction level of first-time guests in ecotourism destinations in Western Visayas grouped according to age was not significant. This is shown in the *p*-value results of 0.061.

Table 7. One-Way ANOVA Results for the Satisfaction Level of First-time Guests in Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas Grouped According to Age

	<i>F</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation
Age			
25 yrs old and below	3.47	0.063	Not Significant
26 – 35 yrs old.			
36 – 45 yrs old.			
46 – 55 yrs old.			
56 and above			

Differences in the Satisfaction Level of First-time Guests in Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas according to educational attainment.

The one-way ANOVA results in Table 8 revealed that the satisfaction level of First-time Guests in ecotourism destinations in Western Visayas grouped according to educational attainment was not significant. This is shown in the *p*-value results of 0.675.

Table 8. One-Way ANOVA results for the Differences in the Satisfaction Level of First-time Guests in Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas Grouped According to Educational Attainment

	<i>F</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation
Educational Attainment			
Bachelor's Degree			
Master's Degree			
Doctorate's Degree	0.73	0.675	Not Significant
Others			

Differences in the Satisfaction Level of First-time Guests in Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas grouped according to monthly salary.

The one-way ANOVA results in Table 7 revealed that the satisfaction level of first-time guests in ecotourism destinations in Western Visayas grouped according to monthly salary was not significant. This is shown in the *p*-value results of 0.589.

Table 9. One-Way ANOVA results for the Differences in the Satisfaction Level of First-time Guests in Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas Grouped According to Monthly Salary

	<i>F</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation
Monthly Salary			
Php 14,999.00 and below			
Php 15,000.00 - 24,999.00			
Php 25,000.00 – 34,999.00	0.611	0.589	Not Significant
Php 35,000.00 – 44,999.00			
Php 45,000.00 and above			

Differences in the Emotional Response of First-time Guests in Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas according to gender.

The *t*-test results in Table 10 showed significant differences in the emotional response of first-time guests in ecotourism destinations in Western Visayas according to gender. This is shown in the *p*-value results of 0.000.

Table 10. *t*-test results for the Differences in the Emotional Response of First-time Guests in Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas Grouped According to Gender

	Mean	<i>t</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation
Gender				
Male	3.19			
Female	3.26	45.38*	0.000	Significant

Differences in the Emotional Response of First-time Guests in Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas according to age.

The one-way ANOVA results in Table 11 revealed that the emotional response of first-time guests in ecotourism destinations in Western Visayas grouped according to age was not significant. This is shown in the *p*-value results of 0.078.

Table 11. One-Way ANOVA results for the Differences in the Emotional Response of First-time Guests in Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas Grouped According to Age

	<i>F</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation
Age			
25 yrs old and below			
26 – 35 yrs old.			
36 – 45 yrs old.	2.65	0.078	Not Significant
46 – 55 yrs old.			
56 and above			

Differences in the Emotional Response of First-time Guests in Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas according to educational attainment.

The one-way ANOVA results in Table 12 revealed that the emotional response of first-time guests in ecotourism destinations in Western Visayas grouped according to educational attainment was not significant. This is shown in the *p*-value results of 0.059.

Table 12. One-Way ANOVA results for the Differences in the Emotional Response First-time Guests in Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas Grouped According to Educational Attainment

	<i>F</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation
Educational Attainment			
Bachelor's Degree			
Master's Degree			
Doctorate's Degree	2.69	0.059	Not Significant
Others			

Differences in the Emotional Response of First-time Guests in Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas according to a monthly salary.

The one-way ANOVA results in Table 13 revealed that significant differences existed in the emotional response of first-time guests in ecotourism destinations in Western Visayas grouped according to a monthly salary. This is shown in the *p*-value results of 0.008.

Table 13. One-Way ANOVA results for the Differences in the Emotional Response of First-time Guests in Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas Grouped According to Monthly Salary

	<i>F</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation
Monthly Salary			
Php 14,999.00 and below			
Php 15,000.00 - 24,999.00			
Php 25,000.00 – 34,999.00	4.36*	0.008	Significant
Php 35,000.00 – 44,999.00			
Php 45,000.00 and above			

Post-Hoc results in Table 14 revealed significant differences in the emotional response of first-time guests in ecotourism destinations in Western Visayas earning P14,999 and below and those earning P 25,000 – P34,999. This is shown by *the p*-value result of 0.010, which is higher than 0.05.

Table 14. Post-Hoc results for the Differences in the Emotional Response First-time Guests in Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas Grouped According to Monthly Salary

	P 14,999 & below	P 15,000-24,999	P 25,000-34,999	P 35,000-44,999	P 45,000 & above
P 14,999 & below	-	0.220	0.009	0.072	0.116
P 15,000-24,999	0.220	-	0.325	0.817	0.730
P 25,000-34,999	0.009	0.325	-	1.000	0.995
P 35,000-44,999	0.730	0.817	1.000	-	0.990
P 45,000 & above	0.116	0.730	0.995	0.990	-

Differences in the Behavioral Intentions of First-time Guests in Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas according to gender.

The *t*-test results in Table 6 showed significant differences in the behavioral intentions of first-time guests in ecotourism destinations in Western Visayas grouped according to gender. This is shown in the *p*-value results of 0.000.

Table 15. t-test results for the Differences in the Behavioral Intentions of First-time Guests in Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas Grouped According to Gender

	Mean	<i>t</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation
Gender				
Male	4.12	43.56*	0.000	Significant
Female	4.03			

Differences in the Behavioral Intentions of First-time Guests in Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas according to age.

The one-way ANOVA results in Table 16 revealed significant differences in the behavioral intentions of first-time guests in ecotourism destinations grouped according to age. This is shown in the *p*-value results of 0.005.

Table 16. One-Way ANOVA Results for the Differences in the Behavioral Intentions of First-time Guests in Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas Grouped According to Age

	<i>F</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation
Age			
25 yrs old and below	4.25*	0.005	Significant
26 – 35 yrs old.			
36 – 45 yrs old.			
46 – 55 yrs old.			
56 and above			

Post-Hoc results in Table 17 showed significant differences in the behavioral intentions of first-time guests 25 years and below and all other age groups. First-time guests who were 25 years old and below were significantly different in terms of work performance with those who were 26-35 years

old ($p=0.039$), 36-45 years old ($p=0.020$), 46-55 yrs old ($p=0.006$), and first-time guests who were 56 years old and above ($p=0.036$).

Table 17. Post-Hoc results for the Differences in the Behavioral Intentions of First-time Guests in Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas Grouped According to Age

	25 yrs old & below	26-35 yrs old	36-45 yrs old	46-55 yrs old	56 yrs old & above
25 yrs old & below	-	0.039	0.020	0.006	0.036
26-35 yrs old	0.039	-	0.966	0.546	1.000
36-45 yrs old	0.020	0.966	-	0.918	0.995
46-55 yrs old	0.006	0.546	0.918	-	0.767
56 yrs old & above	0.036	1.000	0.995	0.767	-

Differences in the Behavioral Intentions of First-time Guests in Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas according to educational attainment.

The one-way ANOVA results in Table 18 revealed that the first-time guests in ecotourism destinations in Western Visayas grouped according to educational attainment were insignificant. This is shown in the p -value results of 0.123.

Table 18. Differences in the Behavioral Intentions of First-time Guests in Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas According to Educational Attainment

	F -value	p -value	Interpretation
Educational Attainment			
Bachelor's Degree			
Master's Degree			
Doctorate's Degree	3.10	0.123	Not Significant
Others			

Differences in the Behavioral Intentions of First-time Guests in Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas Grouped According to Monthly Salary

The one-way ANOVA results in Table 19 revealed that Behavioral Intentions of First-time Guests in Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas Grouped According to Monthly Salary were insignificant. This is shown in the p -value results of 0.076.

Table 19. One-Way ANOVA results for the Differences in the Behavioral Intentions of First-time Guests in Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas Grouped According to Monthly Salary

	<i>F</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation
Monthly Salary			
Php 14,999.00 and below			
Php 15,000.00 - 24,999.00			
Php 25,000.00 – 34,999.00	2.27	0.076	Not Significant
Php 35,000.00 – 44,999.00			
Php 45,000.00 and above			

Relationship between satisfaction level, emotional response, and behavioral intentions of first-time guests in ecotourism destinations in Western Visayas

Data in table 20 showed a significant relationship between satisfaction level and emotional response, $r = 0.000$, satisfaction level and behavioral intentions, $r = 0.036$, and emotional response and behavioral intentions, $r = 0.000$.

Table 20. Pearson’s r results for the relationship Between Satisfaction Level, Emotional Response, and Behavioral Intentions of First-time Guests in Ecotourism Destinations in Western Visayas

	Organizational Commitment	Job Satisfaction	Work Performance
Organizational Commitment	-	0.000	0.036
Job Satisfaction	0.000	-	0.000
Work Performance	0.036	0.000	-

Generally, first-time guests in ecotourism destinations in Western Visayas were satisfied.

First-time guests in ecotourism destinations in Western Visayas exhibited moderate positive emotion. In terms of behavioral intentions of first-time guests in ecotourism destinations in Western Visayas were strongly agree as assessed by the respondents.

Gender is a factor found to have a significant influence on satisfaction levels. However, age, educational attainment, and monthly salary were factors found not to have a significant influence on satisfaction level. Gender and monthly salary are factors found to have a significant influence on emotional job response. However, age and educational attainment were factors found not to have a significant influence on emotional response.

Gender and age are factors found to have a significant influence on the behavioral intentions of hospitality educators. On the other hand, educational attainment and monthly salary are not factors that significantly influence behavioral intentions. Significant relationships existed between satisfaction level and emotional response, satisfaction level and behavioral intentions, and emotional response and behavioral intentions.

CONCLUSION

It can be construed that the ecotourism destination operators in Western Visayas emphasized providing all the desired satisfaction levels or desires of clients regardless of whether new guests or not. New guests exhibited moderate positive emotions. The positive emotional responses of customers were congruent with their level of satisfaction in terms of the products/services provided for them during their stay.

New guests' moderately agreed behavioral intention to recommend or refer to the ecotourism destination in Western Visayas is assumed to have come from their expectations to have attained a much better service than commercialized establishments and several limitations, such as limited activities and product offerings.

Findings revealed that gender has a significant influence on satisfaction levels. Findings also revealed that male new guests have slightly higher satisfaction than male new guests. It can therefore be construed that there is greater sensitivity among male new guests to appreciate ecotourism destinations.

Gender and monthly salary were factors found to have a significant influence on emotional response. Therefore, the emotional response differs for male and female new guests or new guests earning 45,000 and above, 35,000-44,999, 25,000-34,999, 15,000-24,999, or 14,999 and below.

Gender and age were factors found to have a significant influence on behavioral intentions. It was also revealed that males would most likely recommend the ecotourism destinations more than

females, and new guests who are older and seeks a refreshing nature experience will most likely recommend the ecotourism destinations in Western Visayas as compared to younger ones.

Significant relationships existed across all variables between satisfaction level, emotional response, and behavioral intentions. Therefore it follows that satisfaction level determines emotional response and behavioral intentions; emotional response determines satisfaction level and behavioral intention; and behavioral intentions determine emotional response and satisfaction level.

REFERENCES

- Del Castillo, C. J. C., Libao, M. F., Chua, A. K. A., De, K. D., Guzman, E. S. D., & Liba, R. T. (2016). Level of satisfaction, emotional responses and behavioural intentions of first-visit customers of selected restaurants in Quezon City, Philippines. *TEAM Journal of Hospitality and Tourism*, 13(1), 65-72.
- Fishbein, M., & Ajzen, I. (2011). *Predicting and changing behavior: The reasoned action approach*. Psychology press.
- Heung, V. C., & Gu, T. (2012). Influence of restaurant atmospherics on patron satisfaction and behavioral intentions. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 31(4), 1167-1177.
- Jaafar, S. N. (2010). *The Relationships between Food Quality, Service Quality, Perceived Value-for-Money, Desires-congruence and Self-congruence on Consumer Satisfaction and In Turn Lead to Behavioural Intentions and Consumers' Post-purchase Attitude in the Restaurant Industry*. University of Surrey (United Kingdom).
- Josiam, B. M., & Henry, W. (2014). Entertainment: Utilitarian and hedonic motivations for patronizing fun experience restaurants. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 144, 187-202.
- Kang, E., Boger, C. A., Back, K. J., & Madera, J. (2011, July). The impact of sensory environments on Spagoers' emotion and behavioral intention. In *16th Graduate Students Research Conference*. From http://scholarworks.umass.edu/gradconf_hospitality/2011/Presentation/77.
- Lin, I. Y., & Mattila, A. S. (2010). Restaurant servicescape, service encounter, and perceived congruency on customers' emotions and satisfaction. *Journal of hospitality marketing & management*, 19(8), 819-841.
- Mehrabian, A., & Russell, J. A. (1974). *An approach to environmental psychology*. the MIT Press.
- Othman, M., & Goodarzirad, B. (2013). Restaurant color's as stimuli to enhance pleasure feeling and its effect on diners' behavioral intentions in the family chain restaurants. *Journal of Tourism, Hospitality & Culinary Arts (JTHCA)*, 5(1), 75-101.

Declaration of Conflicting Interest. There are no conflicts concerning this research paper, authorship, and publication.

Funding. No funding from external sources, such as donations or grants, was received for conducting research, authorship, and publication of this paper.